

THE CONCEPT OF COMPETENCE AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN MUSIC LESSONS

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Annotation: In this article, theoretical information is provided on the formation of national and general cultural competence in students through music lessons.

Key words: lesson, music, culture, technologies, competence, educational system.

Music plays an important role in the formation of a person; actively affects his emotions and psyche. Bringing to the world of sophistication from the basic situations of general education schools and providing spiritual education. In this, the teacher introduces the children to an important piece of music and plays it expressively "live", attracting the attention of the students, developing their speech, thinking ability, broadening their world view, emotional feelings as well. actively affects. The content of music lessons includes not only mastering, but also development of students' consciousness, attitude to reality, formation of aesthetic culture and formation of other internal feelings.

The process of interaction between the teacher and the student in the music lesson is based on personal communication. The music teacher directs and supervises the musical activities of all students in the lesson without exception. It also supports communication and mutual control among students. The work of the teacher in the lesson creates the ground for all students to acquire the basics of knowledge, to develop the necessary skills and qualifications in the lesson itself.

Each music lesson should enrich students with new knowledge, expand their horizons, develop musical skills and abilities, or improve what they have learned before.

Music lessons provide for the comprehensive development of students in the field of music, and create a foundation for their musical culture.

A music lesson gives a feeling of understanding the joy of music creation. The ability to enjoy the moral-aesthetic content of a composer's or folk music creates a sense of beauty and bravery. In the lesson, all types of creative activity that are strongly connected with each other will be effective.

At the same time, it is necessary that the lesson, with its content, methods, and organization, has an educational impact on students, forming in them a scientific outlook, ideological beliefs, and personal moral qualities.

In the lesson, it should be carried out jointly and interactively with education, training, development, creative development of students. This is one of the most important principles of music pedagogy.

As in all subjects, the main task was to re-form musical education on a national basis. Accordingly, new educational programs and textbooks on music were created, and work on the improvement of departments is still ongoing.

The school prepares teachers for professional music activities. However, the ability to understand music, perceive it and be creatively influenced by it is essential for every student, whether he will be a professional musician in the future or the basic knowledge, skills and competences of musical-aesthetic activity in the most diverse forms of music culture. It must be unique regardless of whether it remains a well-trained listener.

The unique aspect of the music lesson is that the active form of music education at school involves group singing. Singing as a group with deep folk traditions develops not only musical abilities, but also the quality of character, outlook, artistic taste, fantasy, and aesthetic sense. Singing in a group combines various forms of work carried out in the lesson: ensemble performance, music literacy, music perception, playing musical instruments, vocal performance.

The content of the musical work affects the general culture of the listener, and in turn, the level of activity of the listener's attention. It is well known that listeners who are trained in music have a richer perception. A student who understands music is distinguished by a high level of artistic taste, has the ability to re-experience as a listener based on the understanding of the unique aspect of the form of music, its content, the history of the development of music, has developed skills and competencies in the field of musical-creative activity. It is only on the basis of listening that a piece of music can be fully understood. The purpose of the music lesson is largely focused on the spiritual development of the school student. The development and enrichment of musical and creative abilities should be carried out according to a well-thought-out and consistent system of forming the skills of music perception, looking at the art of music with interest, and developing the artistic hobby of students. Skillfully combining work in a team, group and individually is the main issue in the organization of the lesson. In order for the student to be able to organize, plan and complete educational tasks, it is important to teach him to work both as a team and individually.

Any lesson requires that the students of the school monitor the educational activities of the student. This allows us to visualize the nature of learning and learning materials, the process of formation of learning and skills. Students of the school can analyze the progress of the study, allow the teacher to make appropriate corrections in order to develop the positive aspects of the lesson and reduce the observed negative situations. The task of music lessons is to teach children to actively relate to beauty, to approach music creatively. Today's music lesson should solve this task, and the more actively and purposefully it solves this task, the higher the level of providing only musical education to schoolchildren will be. Like any subject teacher, a music teacher's professional direction plays an important role in the system of evaluating the personality of a music teacher, and the need for pedagogical activity is based on it. It has: children's interest and love, passion for pedagogical work, psychological and pedagogical intelligence and observation, pedagogical etiquette, pedagogical imagination, organizational skills, honesty, sincerity, demandingness and determination, stability, restraint, endurance, It embodies having an opinion about oneself, professional work ability, spiritual, first of all, the need and interest to know, intellectual activity, the ability to feel novelty, preparation for the independent development of pedagogical knowledge. Music actively develops children's feelings, especially emotional and aesthetic feelings. Music stimulates the development of a child's creative talent. Music actively affects the child's soul, plays an important role in the formation of his moral and aesthetic image. Therefore, the main

goal of music education is to educate students in musical culture, which is a component of human spiritual culture. To achieve these goals, the music teacher has the following tasks:

- increasing students' interest in the art of music;
- development of musical artistic taste and the need for musical activities;
- composition of the range of knowledge and skills about music;
- development of feelings of artistic creativity during music activities;
- moral and aesthetic education of children through the artistic and ideological content of the works;
- instilling enthusiasm for profession and work during music lessons.

The professional level of a music teacher is important in the implementation of these tasks.

In conclusion, it is not a secret today that the future perspective of the country depends on the education of the students of the music class and the development of all-rounded perfect people. Every pedagogue should feel this clearly and clearly.

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